

THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS AND INTERNATIONAL COMMUNITY ORGANIZATIONS ON THE LIVES OF PERSONS WITH PHYSICAL DISABILITIES IN RURAL AND URBAN YEMENI SOCIETY - FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE JOB STAFF - A FIELD STUDY

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Abstract

The current research aimed to identify the impact of government institutions and international community organizations on the lives of persons with physical disabilities in (rural and urban) Yemeni society, from the perspective of the staff working in them. The researchers used a descriptive-analytical approach. A questionnaire was prepared consisting of (36) paragraphs, divided into four axes (health, educational, employment, and political). The questionnaire was applied to a sample of 120 workers. They were selected in a simple random manner from some government institutions and international community organizations located in six governorates: (Sana'a Capital, Aden, Saada, Al-Dali', Amran, and Sana'a Governorate). One of the most prominent results of the research was the impact of government institutions and international community organizations on the lives of persons with physical disabilities in rural and urban Yemeni society, from the perspective of its workers, in all the axes covered by the research came with an average estimate, in terms of the arithmetic mean of (3.02), the standard deviation (1.14), and a percentage of (60.4%). It was found that there were no statistically significant differences between the responses of the sample members about the impact of government institutions and international community organizations in achieving a decent life and equal opportunities for persons with physical disabilities in (rural and urban) Yemeni society, according to the variable (gender, governorate, academic qualification, and duration of service). It was found that there are differences according to the job grade variable in favor of (the director of a department, and the head of a department). The research concluded by presenting some recommendations and suggestions that contribute to enhancing the positive impact of government institutions and international community organizations in achieving a decent life and equal opportunities for persons with physical disabilities in (rural/urban) Yemeni society.

Keywords: Government Institutions, International Community Organizations, Physical Disabilities, Rural and Urban, Yemeni Society, Job Staff.

INTRODUCTION

During the past decade, several global changes and developments have occurred that have had repercussions and effects on the Arab countries. Some of these changes are known as the Arab Spring revolutions, which have exhausted the countries that have coexisted with these revolutions and made them live in tragic difficult situations as a result of the armed conflict that they have fought and are still fighting until now, which in turn led to unrest in various social, economic and political aspects. In particular, it has greatly affected the role of government institutions and organizations of the international community in providing services to society in general, and the disabled in society in particular.

Disability is one of the most important social problems experienced by developed and developing countries alike, and therefore global attention has increased to the category of persons with disabilities, their care policies, and affirmation of their rights, and urging countries to provide them with a decent life and equal opportunities as citizens with the rights that the average citizen has, and they have the duties stipulated in international, regional and local constitutions, especially in light of the high percentage of persons with disabilities at the global, regional and local levels and the frightening increase in their numbers, especially in light of the situations and conflicts that affect the whole world, which doubles the opportunity to increase the numbers of this category [1].

Because of the importance of social integration of persons with physical disabilities, developed and developing countries have attached great importance to it, and with the entry of the third millennium, and the accompanying changes and developments, covering all areas of life, countries have worked on a radical review of their systems to keep pace with all areas of integration [2].

The principle of the inclusion of persons with physical disabilities in society is an urgent issue, and for service providers with special needs to ensure the success of integration, barriers, and needs must be considered, and then a set of programs that prepare the integration process must be carefully planned [3].

The Problem of the Study:

The war that was launched in Yemen from March 26, 2015, through the six wars of Saada until 2010, and before that the war of the summer of 1994, and the wars of the central regions left many disabilities, especially physical, and the consequent psychological, social, and economic effects, and a wave of displacement for many persons with physical disabilities from conflict areas in search of security areas.

The disabled person finds himself in a new environment that is completely different from the environment in which he lived and is accustomed to its conditions, but now he is in a new environment that has different characteristics and conditions [4].

As well as the denial of public rights, in political rights, their opportunities for nomination and candidacy are still limited, as there are no legal articles under the current laws on elections and political parties that guarantee the right of persons with disabilities to elections according to their special needs [5].

Here, the importance of the impact of government institutions and organizations of the international community in achieving a decent life and equal opportunities for persons with physical disabilities appears, in terms of rehabilitation or training, education, and achieving the requirements for the process of integrating them into society, and with the most basic elements necessary for persons with physical disabilities.

Therefore, state institutions must work to prepare institutions, organizations, health, sports, transportation, and other facilities in a way that suits the ability of persons with physical disabilities to move in these facilities easily and smoothly, as they represent the largest obstacles facing the process of integration of persons with physical disabilities.

In light of the above, the problem of the study can be formulated in the following two main questions:

- 1) What is the impact of government institutions and international community organizations on the lives of persons with physical disabilities in (rural-urban) Yemeni society from the perspective of (the job staff) working in it?
- 2) Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the averages of the respondents' responses about the impact of government institutions and international community organizations in achieving a decent life and equal opportunities for persons with physical disabilities in (rural-urban) Yemeni society according to the research variables: (government institution, international community organizations, gender, governorate, educational qualification, job grade, duration of service)?

The Objectives of the Study:

This research seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- Identify the impact of government institutions and international community organizations on the lives of persons with physical disabilities in (rural-urban) Yemeni society from the perspective of (the job staff) working in it.
- Identifying the existence of statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the averages of the responses of the sample members about the impact of government institutions and international community organizations on the lives of persons with physical disabilities in (rural-urban) Yemeni society according to the research variables.

The Significance of the Study:

The importance of the current research lies in the following:

- The level of care for the disabled is a basic criterion for measuring the civilization and development of nations. The integration of persons with disabilities into society is one of the priorities of States with their official and national institutions, which stems from the legitimacy of the right of persons with disabilities to equal opportunities in all areas of life and to live in dignity and freedom.
- The current research is an enrichment for the Yemeni and Arab Library on the impact of government institutions, international community organizations, and the concept of care and integration in public life, and will open the way for scholars and researchers to carry out much relevant research.
- Providing many recommendations and suggestions that improve the capabilities and capabilities of decision-makers in government institutions and international community organizations in how to achieve a decent life and equal opportunities for persons with disabilities in society in a scientifically developed manner.

Limitations of the Study:

The current research is determined in the following:

- **Objective limit:** The research was limited to studying the impact of government institutions and international community organizations in achieving a decent life and equal opportunities for persons with physical disabilities in (rural-urban) Yemeni society.

- **Human Limit:** The research was limited to a sample of (job staff) working in government institutions and international community organizations in six governorates, male and female.
- **Spatial limitation:** The research was limited to official government institutions and international community organizations that work to achieve a decent life and equal opportunities for persons with physical disabilities in society and are located in several Yemeni governorates, namely (Sana'a - a political capital and its countryside Saada, Aden - an economic capital and its countryside Al-Dali').
- **Time limit:** The research was carried out during the year 2023/2024.

Terms of the Study:

- 1) Government institutions are defined as a public administrative organization that enjoys legal personality and financial and administrative independence and is linked to the central administrative authorities concerned with the relationship of dependency and subject to administrative control, and it is managed in a decentralized administrative manner to achieve specific objectives in its legal system [6].

The researchers define government institutions as those official Yemeni institutions that work to provide social welfare services for persons with physical disabilities to integrate them into society, and they are supervised by the Ministry of Social Affairs and Labor or by the Prime Minister directly or the Supreme Council for Humanitarian Affairs.

- 2) Definition of the international community: It is the entities and units that exist at the international level as distinct from those that exist at the internal level, so this community consists primarily of states, then international organizations, and some other entities that have imposed themselves as influential in international relations, such as multinational companies and national liberation movements, provided that these relations are regulated by international law [7].

Researchers know the international community: as the sum of the independent international political entities that are subject in their relations among themselves to international law, where it is divided into persons with international legal personality.

- 3) Persons with physical disabilities: They are those who suffer from a bony, muscular, or neurological disability or a chronic medical condition that limits their ability to use their bodies normally, which negatively affects their ability to participate in life activities [8].

Researchers define a physical disability as a person with a physical disability whose degree varies according to the type of physical disability, which may affect the child, young person, or adult in one of their physical devices so that they cause a partial physical disability in one of the lists or more than one list.

Previous Studies:

- The study [9] aimed to identify the reality of social care and its role in the rehabilitation of persons with disabilities from the perspective of the disabled themselves in the Aden governorate. The descriptive-analytical and historical approach was used. The study relied on the interview and questionnaire for (100)

disabled persons. One of its most prominent results was the weakness of the community care that the disabled receive and its role in rehabilitating them in society in its various forms and in the basic areas of life.

- The study [10] aimed to identify the role of local and international organizations in the integration of persons with physical disabilities in the fields (social, cultural, educational, health, employment, sports, recreational, and political), from the perspective of the staff of organizations of persons with physical disabilities in the capital Sana'a. The descriptive analytical approach was used, and a measurement tool was built consisting of two questionnaires, the first: for the staff of organizations, consisting of (86) paragraphs, and the second: for persons with physical disabilities, consisting of (85) paragraphs, and the research sample consisted of (183) male and female employees, and (229) disabled persons. One of the most prominent results of the study was that there is a below-average (weak) level in the role played by organizations working in the field of disability in the integration of persons with physical disabilities in social, cultural, educational, health, employment, sports, recreational and political integration, from the perspective of both samples.
- The study [11] sought to identify the obstacles facing the rehabilitation of the disabled in Yemeni society - a sociological vision from the perspective of social service. One of the most prominent results of the study was the lack of cooperation of families of the disabled with institutions for the care and rehabilitation of the disabled, and the lack of coordination between institutions concerned with the care of the disabled. The researcher made some recommendations, including developing legislation that helps persons with disabilities to shift from consumed energies to productive units by training them in professions commensurate with their abilities, achieving professional and educational competence, providing free health, psychological, and social care, and providing prosthetic devices such as artificial limbs, hearing aids or belts, which represent an obstacle for persons with disabilities from low-income families.
- The study [12] dealt with Identifying the role played by NGOs in the field of rehabilitation of persons with physical disabilities in the United States of America, Japan, and the Arab Republic of Egypt, the study used the comparative approach, and a questionnaire was applied to a sample of specialists and professionals. One of the most prominent results of the study was the weakness of the administrative capabilities of NGOs, the absence of administrative competencies capable of working either through volunteering or employment, and the inability of care and rehabilitation institutions for special categories to absorb all applicants from those categories, which increases their number every year, which limits the provision of services to them.
- The study [13] aimed to identify the role of centers in providing educational, health, guidance, and counseling services, social integration, and vocational training to persons with disabilities. The study used the descriptive survey approach to collect and interpret data. One of the most prominent results of the study was: the high rates of disability among the poor, as shown by the high rates of disability among the children of illiterate mothers and fathers, and the lower the disability, the higher the educational and cultural level of parents.

- The study [14] aimed to identify the effectiveness of institutions for the care of persons with physical disabilities in their social integration. The descriptive survey approach was used, and the study sample consisted of (8) organizations working in the field of community integration and care of persons with physical disabilities in Aswan Governorate. One of the most prominent results of the study was that there are factors that lead to an increase in the ability of institutions to bring about a change in the social status of the beneficiaries by (92.8%), and one of the most important of these factors was the acquisition of self-esteem values for the disabled, and that there are factors that lead to an increase in the ability of institutions to bring about a change in behavior for the beneficiaries by (89.3%), including respect for the opinions of others, and participation in social activities, and that there are factors that lead to an increase in the ability of institutions to help confront problems for the beneficiaries by a likely rate of (90%), and from these factors benefit from the experiences of others.
- The study [1] aimed to identify the role of social welfare policies for the disabled and the extent of their success in rehabilitating and integrating the disabled in an urban environment in Algerian society. The descriptive analytical approach was used, and the questionnaire was applied as a tool for data collection. One of the most important results of the study: It was found that the urban environment helps to facilitate the process of social integration of persons with physical disabilities, and it was found that the care provided to persons with disabilities is very few compared to the size and number of persons with disabilities in Algerian cities so that the majority of persons with disabilities do not benefit from it, which leads them to seclusion, isolation and escape from society.
- The study [15] aimed to identify the reality of integrating persons with physical disabilities into the local community environmentally and socially (Nablus Governorate case study). The two-pronged interview form that was conducted with the study sample was used, namely: Disabled persons and officials of Palestinian institutions (public, private) in Nablus Governorate. One of the most prominent results of the study was that disabled persons in Nablus Governorate did not reach the stage of full social integration, and that legislation suffers from weak application on the ground at all urban and social levels.
- The study [16] aimed to identify the results of the major changes that took place in the life of society in the composition of the legislation in 1990 of the Americans with Disabilities Act. The study showed that the health and social services provided to the disabled do not meet their needs. The study concluded that there are some prevailing beliefs and values in the fabric of American life that stand in the way of meeting the health, social, economic, and professional needs of persons with disabilities. This study recommends the need to provide health, social, economic, and professional care for persons with disabilities.
- The study [17] aimed to identify the obstacles that limit the participation of women with physical disabilities in work. One of the most important results of the study was that one of the most important obstacles that hinder women with physical disabilities from joining work is the effort and time, as well as the restrictions and barriers imposed by disability on women with physical disabilities, as well as the characteristics of women themselves. The study recommended the provision of vocational training for women and the provision of financial resources, time,

equipment, and vocational trainers to qualify women with disabilities professionally to work.

Benefiting from previous studies: the previous studies have been used to enhance the theoretical and intellectual framework on the concept of social care and integration, its types and forms, and what is physically disabled, and to obtain some definitions and main divisions of the research topic, and in how to build paragraphs of the scale and methods of processing statistics and methods of data analysis. Previous studies have also contributed to drawing attention to many scientific sources needed by the current research.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

First: Theoretical Framework for Social Inclusion:

- 1. The concept of social inclusion:** Integration focuses on providing support to students with special needs in a framework outside the regular classroom system and aims to change the student's performance to become more appropriate to the education system in the regular classroom [18].
- 2. Inclusion means** the process by which an individual can adapt to the social environment in which he or she lives by adhering to its rules and regulations. Social integration is defined as a process similar to the process of socialization, the latter includes the processes of teaching, learning, education, training, preparation, formation, and normalization, through which the individual can introduce the culture of his society with its multiple elements, and thus transform from a mere biological organism to a social organism, and means that social integration is social normalization [19]. Researchers believe that the concept of social integration: Is an intentional social process that aims to achieve autonomy, self-adaptation, psychological, and social for the individual, thanks to many social, psychological, health, and professional programs and services, and to live a positive and effective social life in his family, school, professional or public group.
- 3. The importance of social integration:** the importance of social integration lies in the fact that it is limited to the disabled individual only. Social integration is a natural result of the interaction that takes place between the individual and his social surroundings. Therefore, the type of integration that has become common and desirable in the world is mutual readjustment (adapting the disabled person to his disability and his society and adapting the latter to it). This type includes compensating the deficiency suffered by the disabled person, to absorb him from the productive system. The process of social integration expands from the individual's family to the group of his companions, and then to the school. It includes those around him as a whole and this is during his life. The importance of social integration also lies in that it is a process that is not limited to one period of the individual's life. Rather, it is continuous and in which the rules and systems of society are adopted, and all forms of behavior and ways of thinking are learned. Social integration also contributes to the acquisition by the disabled individual of the culture of the society in which he lives. This is to build part of the personality of the disabled individual through social integration, and social adaptation is achieved through the introduction of the values that exist in his surroundings, and their integration into the education of his personality with the groups that end [20].

4. Forms of inclusion in society: Forms of inclusion in society include:

- a) **Health inclusion:** disabled persons have the right to special treatment and education, as they have the right to medical, psychological, and functional treatment, including prosthetic organs, orthotics, medical and therapeutic rehabilitation, as well as early detection of the type of disability [21].
- b) **Educational inclusion:** The Council for Extraordinary Children (CEC) defined educational inclusion as a belief that involves placing extraordinary children with ordinary children in the regular classroom or the least restrictive educational environment for the extraordinary child; so that the integration is either temporary or permanent, provided that factors are provided to help the success of this concept [22].
- c) **Vocational and functional integration:** vocational integration is the last step for the disabled individual after completing the training and rehabilitation process, by providing him with a job position commensurate with his physical and mental abilities, and the individual is considered integrated in his work if work means a lot to him, but integration in this sense is only quantitative, and integration can be seen as consisting of three manifestations: the meaning that is related to work, the feeling of unity with work or approaching work and its organizations, and the degree to which it is considered the main concern in life [1].
- d) **Political Inclusion:** The International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) is a catalyst not only for the movement of persons with disabilities but also for many organizations working in the field. The rights of persons with disabilities do not differ from others in principle, and although they differ in some details, they are entitled to enjoy all the rights contained in the human rights charters. However, persons with disabilities have suffered from a great deprivation of basic rights, especially civil rights, as participation requires an acceptable limit of capabilities, influence, and control, it also requires more economic, social, and political empowerment, and this means politically the freedom to choose to change rulers at every level, starting from the head of the Municipal Persons's Assembly to the President of the Republic [23].

Second: Theoretical Framework for Physical Disability:

- 1) **The concept of physical disability:** The Ministry of Social Affairs, through the association for the disabled, indicated that it is: a loss of psychological or physiological function, and that it is the disability resulting from functional inability to perform certain activities, and this disability or deficiency prevents the individual from performing his role as an ordinary person in his society on one hand or in several aspects, including social and cultural [24]. However, a person with a disability can be seen as suffering from social deficiencies and poor performance. It is characterized by a person who suffers from a disability that represents a deficiency or lack of function of the body that belongs to one of the body's systems. It is also characterized by a person who is unable to carry out the normal functions of daily life, a person who needs the help of others, and a person whose organic disability affects him according to its degree in terms of simplicity or severity and in terms of the age at which the disability occurred [25].

2) Classification of physical disability: is classified according to the nature and level of injury and according to the location of the injury or injured organs that led to the physical disability, including injuries to the central nervous system; and includes: cerebral palsy, spastic palsy, spinal fissure, spinal cord injury, epilepsy, hydrocephalus, polio; and falls into this category: deformity and amputation of the limbs, hip inflammation, osteoarthritis, congenital hip dislocation, arthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, cleft throat and lip, inclination and deviation of the spine, muscle injuries: this category includes: muscular atrophy, degeneration and atrophy of the muscles of the spinal cord [26].

3) The needs of the physically disabled: social service plays a major role in the process of satisfying these needs, through social welfare programs for the disabled, the most prominent of which can be summarized in the following: medical, health, psychological, social, educational, vocational, work, and employment services [27].

Third: The Reality of Social Integration of Persons with Physical Disabilities in Yemeni Society:

The experience of the Republic of Yemen shows the high rates of disability due to rapid population growth, high poverty rate, illiteracy, and malnutrition. Attention to persons with disabilities has begun by issuing many legislations that guarantee their rights and achieve equal opportunities, including the Republican Decree on the establishment and formation of the National Committee for the Care and Rehabilitation of Persons with Disabilities and the project of the Fund for the Care and Rehabilitation of Persons with Disabilities, which contributed to the coordination and integration of national and international efforts and the improvement of the conditions of persons with disabilities and the access of care, rehabilitation and employment services to the depth of the Yemeni countryside and the desert. The experience of family- and community-based rehabilitation in Yemen began in 1992 with the signing of an agreement between the Ministry of Social Affairs and the Swedish Organization for the Protection of Students. Another agreement was signed between the Ministry and the United Nations Development Programme in 1999. Based on these agreements, the program was implemented in seven mountainous areas that served (438) students and helped their families acquire skills to deal with them. It also qualified them in health, education, and practice, in addition to training teachers and volunteers.

Although the experience is still limited given the size of the disability problem in Yemen, it has contributed to changing society's perception of the disabled and has motivated parents to undertake individual initiatives to provide the necessary funding for the continued success of community-based rehabilitation programs. It has also contributed to the integration of persons with disabilities in regular schools and according to their abilities, and to providing education and training opportunities for families of persons with disabilities [28].

1) The Reality of the Disabled in the Laws and Legislation in Yemen:

Yemen has realized the seriousness of the problem of disability and that the deprivation to which this social segment is exposed is mainly due to the existence of many physical and social barriers that prevent persons with disabilities from accessing the services available in the natural environment to other non-disabled citizens, and the negative effects of the continued existence of these barriers on the rights of persons with disabilities, following the Constitution of the Republic of Yemen, which guarantees the principle of equal opportunities in rights and duties for all citizens

without any discrimination whatsoever, and the negative impact of the continued high rates of deprivation among persons with disabilities on the social, economic and political conditions of persons with disabilities and their families. It has issued several national legislations aimed at reducing disability rates among members of Yemeni society, and at enabling persons with disabilities to overcome these barriers and enjoy their natural rights as members of Yemeni society on the one hand, and to carry out their duties towards society on the other hand, especially since the beginning of 1991. We refer to the following to highlight these legislations according to their chronological sequence, namely: "Presidential Decree No. (5) of 1991 on the establishment and formation of the National Committee for the Care of the Disabled and determining its functions and competence, Presidential Decree No. (6) of 1991 on the establishment of the Fund for the Care of the Disabled, Law No. (61) of 1999 on the Care and Rehabilitation of the Disabled, and Law No. (2) of 2002 on the Fund for the Care and Rehabilitation of the Disabled" [13].

2) The Health Reality of Persons with Physical Disabilities in Yemen:

The government health sector continues to bear the greatest health burdens and its problems worsen day after day due to the scarcity of its resources, the aging of its facilities, and the high cost of medicine, in addition to the high number of persons in need of this service. If the Ministry of Health has recently realized the size of the potential problem and started to develop some material resources through the popular effort and contribute to the cost of the service, this experience needs care, monitoring, and continuous evaluation, recognizing that community contributions have an important and effective impact on the continuation of many health services in recent times, especially with the increase in the cost of treatment, the provision of medical devices, the low levels of income, the lack of external assistance, the inflation of administrative bodies, the deterioration of the price of the national currency, the weakness of official professional institutions and the marginalization of the role of trade union institutions. In addition to all this, the health institution in Yemen has suffered major setbacks resulting from the failure to implement the budget allocated to health or the failure to provide foreign currency, which made this institution unable to provide the most important items that are considered one of the ABCs of medical work, such as: (surgical sutures, medical gauze, antiseptics, serums, field needles, blood proximity, solutions).

In addition to all this, another deterioration has begun since the beginning of the current war, March 26, 2015, which entered its ninth year. All this has made the health sector a sector that cannot meet the most basic elements of the health life of the average individual and diseases that hope to be cured and cured are available. What is the case with the conditions of the disabled, especially those with physical disabilities, in addition to the weak role played by the official authorities responsible for the care and rehabilitation of the disabled, towards this group of the health aspect, where the disabled in urban areas in general and rural areas, in particular, suffer from the lack of health services provided to him. The physically disabled, if he wants to access the Funds for the care and rehabilitation of the disabled in his governorate, bears great suffering physically first, and if he does not receive any services, he moves to the main center in the Sana'a Municipality to be able to obtain a disability card, to diagnose the condition, and then suffers to obtain the simplest health services, and after all this he gets crutches, or a regular chair to be able to move, and return home.

He cannot access health care and health and psychological rehabilitation, whether in these entities or other organizations and associations, whether international or local. International organizations, for example, all their dealings with official and non-governmental national institutions and associations, not with the disabled directly, and this affects the level of access of the disabled to the services provided by these institutions, and government institutions suffer greatly from administrative red tape, and from the lack of control over the work of these institutions, which makes the rights of the disabled significantly wasted, or from the absence of proper planning and plans based on scientific foundations to care for the disabled in general and the physically disabled in particular.

3) The Reality of Inclusion in Education for Persons with Physical Disabilities in Yemen:

It is known that students with physical disabilities suffer less than others with other disabilities because they do not face problems in communicating with teachers or benefiting from the traditional methods and methods of education used in regular schools. The fact is that persons with physical disabilities face other problems than those faced by their colleagues with other disabilities. They and their families suffer greatly in accessing schools, due to the transportation system that does not take into account the needs of persons with physical disabilities, and the presence of engineering obstacles that prevent them from entering and using educational facilities easily. They also suffer from the treatment of their ordinary student colleagues, which is often characterized by marginalization and inferiority, which leads many of them to drop out of education.

We also note the failure of those in charge of educational institutions to play their role towards the physically disabled as necessary, to prepare public schools to suit the special situation of the physically disabled, although there are some rare cases in some schools in the Secretariat of the Capital Sana'a and not in other cities, as well as the lack of this service in rural schools.

4) The Functional Reality of Persons with Physical Disabilities in Yemen:

Although the state has issued legislation through which it has determined that the disabled have an estimated percentage of (5%) to obtain jobs in the government sector, this decision is tainted by many things that make it useless for the disabled. This decision requires many technical and basic things to be done, which result in the preparation of the education sector and the absorption of the disabled in general and the physically disabled in particular, by obtaining an appropriate education, which entitles them to come up with a scientific outcome first, as well as the ability to enter into public or private work second, which is suffered by the majority of the disabled in general and the physically disabled in particular.

As well as one of the things that require it to implement the decision fairly is the access of the disabled to health and vocational rehabilitation appropriately, which did not happen to them or the vast majority of them. The absence of vocational rehabilitation in particular means the failure of the disabled to adapt to the work environment, as well as his suffering in dealing with customers, colleagues, and leadership of this or that institution. In addition to all this, the absence of institutions or their clear shortcomings in the aspect of vocational rehabilitation in particular, whether at the urban level or the rural level, so how can the illiterate or those who only read and write get an appropriate or even inappropriate job benefit him economically and

psychologically, as it has been proven that their impact on improving the psychological aspect of the disabled in general, and the physical disabled in particular. Another thing that requires implementation and approval by the state in coordination with the private sector for the disabled to obtain a similar or close percentage of jobs in the private sector, which is completely absent, and the absence of coordination – also – in preparing the disabled professionally and qualifying and training them to suit work in this sector, which does not do its role towards the disabled.

5) Political Participation of Persons with Physical Disabilities in Yemen:

For a long time, the political activities in our country have been suspended and we do not exercise any of our political rights in general for all components of the persons, and this is the same case for the disabled in general and the physically disabled in particular.

In addition, this group, i.e. the disabled and the physically disabled, do not have any legal legislation that guarantees their right to political practice fairly. Despite their huge numbers, the disabled are considered a vulnerable and marginalized group by the political forces in the country, and they are treated only as numbers to be added to the balances of their nominees and their votes to grab seats, whether in local or parliamentary councils or even in presidential elections.

They are not treated as members of local or parliamentary councils as candidates for them. For this exclusion, the state had to guarantee their right to political participation, by setting a specific percentage for them in local and parliamentary councils (i.e. a quota for the disabled), to force political parties to involve them in real political life, which we hope will happen soon.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

- **Research Methodology:** The descriptive comparative analytical approach was used to answer research questions and achieve its objectives.
- **Research Community:** The current research community consists of (cadres) working in government institutions and international community organizations, which contribute to the provision of care and social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society.
- **Research Sample:** The research was limited to several government institutions and international community organizations that provide care services for the integration of persons with physical disabilities into society, within four Yemeni governorates (Amanat Al-Asimah, Aden, Saada, and Al-Dali'). A sample of its workers was selected by the simple random method, as the sample size reached (120) workers, and Table No. (1) shows this.

Table No (1): It shows the distribution of the sample of employees according to the research variables

Variables		Sex		Total	Percentage
		Male	Female		
Listing Location Governorate:	Sanaa	20	15	35	29%
	Aden	20	15	35	29%
	Sa'adah	15	10	25	21%
	Al-Dhale	15	10	25	21%
	Total	70	50	120	100%
Academic qualification	High school	11	10	21	17.5%
	Bachelor	49	38	87	72.5%
	Postgraduate level	10	2	12	1%
	Total	70	50	120	100%
Position	General Manager	12	2	14	12%
	Department Manager	12	5	17	13%
	Head of Department	12	15	27	22%
	Employee	34	28	62	52%
	Total	70	50	120	100%
Years of service	Less than 5 years	11	4	15	13%
	From 5-10 years	31	16	47	39%
	11 to 15yrs	12	18	30	25%
	Over 15 Years	16	12	28	23%
	Total	70	50	120	100%

- **Building the research tool:** After reviewing what was mentioned in many previous studies related to the research topic, the two researchers prepared a preliminary questionnaire consisting of (40) paragraphs, divided into (4) areas: (health integration, educational integration, functional integration, and political integration).
- **Verifying the validity of the research tool:** The questionnaire was presented to a group of (7) experts specialized in the social, psychological, and linguistic fields at the University of Sana'a. All the amendments submitted by the experts were made, the most prominent of which was the deletion of (4) paragraphs, until the questionnaire consisted of (36) paragraphs, and a correlation coefficient (Pearson) was applied to identify the level of correlation between the questionnaire paragraphs with their axes, at the level of significance (0.05), and table No. (2) shows this.

Table No (2): It shows the validity coefficients between the paragraphs and their correlation with their axes

Paragraph No.	Correlation coefficient	Paragraph No.	Correlation coefficient	Paragraph No.	Correlation coefficient
1	0.644	13	0.806	25	0.792
2	0.702	14	0.970	26	0.680
3	0.631	15	0.644	27	0.823
4	0.731	16	0.736	28	0.797
5	0.834	17	0.707	29	0.749
6	0.722	18	0.853	20	0.674
7	0.754	19	0.720	31	0.840
8	0.602	20	0.607	32	0.778
9	0.723	21	0.703	33	0.686
10	0.711	22	0.800	34	0.835
11	0.806	23	0.621	35	0.652
12	0.727	24	0.710	36	0.672

- **Verifying the stability of the tool:** The stability of the tool was verified by calculating the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, and it was found that the stability coefficients in all research axes are statistically significant at the level of (0.05), where the total stability of the questionnaire reached (0.91), which is a high stability ratio, and meets the purposes of the research, and table No. (3) shows this.

Table No (3): Shows Cronbach's alpha stability coefficients

Axes	Number of paragraphs	Cronbach's Alpha
The role of official institutions in achieving the health integration of persons with physical disabilities in society	8	0.92
The role of official institutions in achieving the educational integration of persons with physical disabilities in society	10	0.90
The role of official institutions in achieving the functional integration of persons with physical disabilities in society	10	0.89
The role of official institutions in achieving the political integration of persons with physical disabilities in society	8	0.90
The total questionnaire	36	0.91

- **Statistical methods:** Statistical package software (SPSS) was used, and many tests were applied to process the data, most notably (arithmetic averages and standard deviations, frequencies and percentages, Cronbach's alpha equation to calculate the total stability of the two scales, Pearson's correlation coefficient, T.test test for one sample, T.test test for two independent samples, One Way Anova analysis to identify the differences between more than two variables, and LSD test to find out in favor of the differences). The study adopted the *five-point Likert scale* as an alternative to the responses of the individuals in kind, and table No. (4) shows this.

Table No (4): shows the distribution of approval scores according to arithmetic averages

Value of substitute	Limits of the arithmetic mean		Grade
	Minimum	ceiling	
1	1	1.80	Very poor
2	1.81	2.60	Weak
3	2.61	3.40	Medium
4	3.41	4.20	High
5	4.21	5	Very High

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Answer to the first question, which reads: "What is the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society from the perspective of their workers?"

The means, standard deviations, and percentages were calculated to show the responses of the sample according to the axes of the questionnaire as a whole, to identify the role of Yemeni official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in society from the perspective of their workers, and Table No. (5) shows the results.

Table No (5): Shows the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in all axes from the perspective of their employees

S/N. Article	Laying Article	Paragraph Text	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	Percentage	Grade
A. The role of official institutions in achieving the health integration of persons with physical disabilities in society:						
1	2	The Foundation provided assistive devices for persons with physical disabilities (chairs, crutches...etc.)	3.56	1.66	71.2%	High
2	6	The Foundation holds many health courses to rehabilitate persons with physical disabilities in the health field.	2.88	0.88	58	Medium
3	1	The Foundation bears the costs of medicines for the disabled	3.64	1.56	73%	High
4	4	The Foundation shall bear the costs of treatment for the physically impaired, whatever these costs may be.	3.27	1.36	65.4%	Medium
5	3	The institution provided inpatient treatment centers to serve persons with physical disabilities.	3.39	1.18	68%	Medium
6	7	The institution transfers difficult cases of physical disabilities for treatment outside the country.	2.48	0.92	50%	Weak
7	5	The Foundation implants prostheses for the physically impaired according to the health report.	3.21	1.31	64%	Medium
8	5	The institution provides all health services for persons with physical disabilities.	3.22	1.22	64%	Medium
Total averages in the health integration axis			3.21	1.26	64.2%	Medium
B. The role of official institutions in achieving the educational integration of persons with physical disabilities in society:						
9	2	The Foundation is keen to enable persons with physical disabilities to obtain public employment.	3.44	1.18	68.8%	Medium
10	5	The Foundation shall provide appropriate vocational rehabilitation for persons with physical disabilities to ensure their success in professional life.	3.22	0.98	64.4%	Medium
11	3	The Foundation is keen on the continuous renewal of programs for the rehabilitation of persons with physical disabilities in vocational rehabilitation.	3.42	0.95	68.4%	Medium
12	1	The Foundation employs 5% of its staff who are disabled.	3.74	0.88	74.8%	Medium
13	4	The institution has the necessary devices and tools for the professional rehabilitation of the disabled.	3.29	1.02	65.8%	Medium
14	6	The institution has qualified cadres capable of rehabilitating the disabled professionally.	3.08	0.88	%62	Medium

15	7	The Foundation works to rehabilitate the physically disabled according to the needs of companies for them.	2.82	1.02	56.4%	Medium
16	8	The Foundation shall provide the necessary facilities for persons with disabilities to obtain a job in private companies.	2.67	0.98	53.4	Medium
17	9	The Foundation supports and encourages small projects for persons with physical disabilities who wish to do so.	2.28	1.00	46%	Low
18	6	The organization markets products produced by the disabled.	3.00	1.06	62%	Medium
Total averages in the educational integration axis			3.09	1.01	%62	Medium
C. The role of official institutions in achieving the functional integration of persons with physical disabilities in society:						
19	7	The Foundation is keen to enable persons with physical disabilities to obtain public employment.	2.49	1.33	50%	Weak
20	4	The Foundation shall provide appropriate vocational rehabilitation for persons with physical disabilities to ensure their success in professional life.	2.58	1.45	62%	Weak
21	6	The Foundation is keen on the continuous renewal of programs for the rehabilitation of persons with physical disabilities in vocational rehabilitation.	2.67	17.1	53.4	Medium
22	4	The Foundation employs 5% of its staff who are disabled.	12.3	1.35	62%	Medium
23		The institution has the necessary devices and tools for the vocational rehabilitation of persons with physical disabilities.	2.34	12.1	47%	Weak
24	1	The institution has qualified cadres capable of rehabilitating the disabled professionally.	3.55	1.22	71%	Medium
25	2	The Foundation works to rehabilitate the physically disabled according to the needs of private companies for them.	3.28	1.29.	65.6%	Medium
26	5	The Foundation shall provide the necessary facilities for persons with disabilities to obtain a job in private companies.	3.02	0.99	60.4	Medium
27	8	The Foundation supports and encourages small projects for persons with physical disabilities who wish to do so.	2,44	0.95	49 %	Low
28	3	The organization markets products produced by the disabled.	3.15	1.05	%63	Medium
Total averages in the functional integration axis			2.86	1.19	57.2%	Medium
D. The role of official institutions in achieving the political integration of persons with physical disabilities into society:						
29	1	The Foundation educates the disabled about their political rights.	3.38	1.43	68%	Medium
30	6	The Foundation works to implement the quota system for persons with physical disabilities in local councils and parliament.	2.79	1.14	56	Medium
31	7	The Foundation works to involve persons with disabilities in national political conferences	2,44	0.95	49 %	Low
32	2	The Foundation is working to establish pressure groups of persons with physical disabilities to amend and enact laws.	3.28	1.29.	65.6%	Medium

33	3	The Foundation contributes to motivating the physically disabled to participate in the elections.	3.02	0.99	60.4	Medium
34	5	The Foundation works to involve persons with disabilities in the membership of the Registration Committee of the Supreme Electoral Commission.	2.82	1.02	56.4%	Medium
35	6	The Foundation works to support the establishment of a union for persons with physical disabilities.	2.79	1.14	56	Medium
36	4	The Foundation lobbies for the full application of international laws relating to the care of the physically impaired.	2.85	1.08	%57	Medium
Total averages in the axis of political integration			2.92	1.09	58.4%	Medium
The sum of the averages in all the axes of the survey as a whole			3.02	1.14	60.4%	Middle

Table (5) shows the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration (integration) of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society from the perspective of their workers, in all the axes covered by the research (health integration, educational integration, functional integration, political integration) came with an average estimate, with an arithmetic average of (3.02), a standard deviation of (1.14) and a percentage of (60.4%).

The researchers attribute this modest result to the general situation that Yemen suffers from in all its governorates as a result of the siege and war, which negatively affected the performance of Yemeni official institutions in providing social care for persons with physical disabilities and their integration into society. It also exacerbated the problem by increasing the number of persons with physical disabilities as a result of various injuries due to the war, which needs to be carefully studied to identify the types of disabilities and their level and severity.

The ranking of the axes of social integration of persons with physical disabilities according to their averages was descending as follows: Health integration achieved the first rank with an average estimate, where the arithmetic mean was (3.21) and a percentage of (64.2%). In the second place, educational integration had an average estimate, where the arithmetic mean was (3.09) and a percentage of (62%). In the third place, political integration came with an average estimate, where the arithmetic mean was (2.92) and a percentage of (58.4%). In the fourth and last place, functional integration had an average estimate, where the arithmetic mean was (2.86) and a percentage of (57.2%).

This result is consistent with the findings of the study [13],[29], which indicated that the level of social integration of persons with physical disabilities came with an average rating, and this is consistent with the result of the study of Al-Omari [30], which concluded that the level of performance of rehabilitation programs in the educational and health aspects was at the average level, while it differed with the study of [10], [12], which concluded that the level of integration of persons with physical disabilities was at a weak level, while the study of Abdul Nour [1] concluded that the level of social integration of persons with physical disabilities was very weak.

Answer to the second question, and a text: "Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the averages of the respondents' responses about the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of

persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the research variables (gender, place of the institution "governorate", educational qualification, job grade, duration of service)?"

- **Identify the nature of the differences in the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society from the perspective of their workers according to the gender variable (males and females).**

To find out the significance of the difference between the arithmetic averages of the responses of the sample of workers in official institutions on the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society, depending on the gender variable, a test was used (T. Test) for two independent samples and Table No. (6) shows this.

Table No (6): (T. Test) to find out the differences in the role of official institutions from the perspective of workers according to gender

Sex	Number	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	Value Tee	Significance level
Males	70	62. 11	11.73	942	0.350
Females	50	58. 56	15. 79		

Table value (t) at a degree of freedom (118) and a level of significance (0. 05 1 99) approx.

It is noted in Table No. (6) that the value of (T. test) extracted was (0. 94), which is smaller than the tabular value of (1. 99) at a degree of freedom (118) and a level of significance (0. 05), and this means that there are no statistically significant differences from the perspective of workers about the role of Yemeni official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the gender variable (males, females).

- **Identify the nature of the differences in the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society from the perspective of their employees according to the variable of the place of the institution (governorate).**

To find out the significance of the difference between the arithmetic averages of the responses of the sample of workers in official institutions on the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society, according to the governorate, a one-way analysis (ANOVA) was used, and Table No. (7) shows this.

Table No (7): shows the analysis of variance to find out the differences in the role of institutions from the perspective of workers according to the governorate

Test	D. Freedom	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F value	Significance level
Between groups	3	31321. 531	16453. 200	37. 23*	.001
Within Groups	11 6	103314. 0	322. 702		
Total	11 9	152133. 6	-		

Table value (Q) at a degree of freedom (2, 152) and a level of significance (0. 05) = (3. 45) Approximately

It is noted in Table No. (7) that the value of (F) extracted was (37. 23) which is less than the tabular value (Q) of (3. 45), with a degree of freedom (2, 152) and a level of significance (0. 05), and this means that there are no statistically significant differences from the perspective of the sample of workers on the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the governorate variable, and this indicates that all state institutions were affected by the siege and the war on Yemen, and therefore the responses of the sample members were very close.

- **Identify the nature of the differences in the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society from the perspective of their employees according to the variable of academic qualification.**

To find out the significance of the difference between the arithmetic means of the responses of the sample of workers on the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with disabilities in Yemeni society, according to the qualification variable (university, bachelor, postgraduate), a one-way analysis (ANOVA) was used, and Table No. (8) shows this.

Table No (8): Single variance analysis to find out the differences in the role of institutions from the perspective of employees according to the qualification

Test	Degree of freedom	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F. value	Significance level
Between Groups	2	293. 681	146. 840	1. 805*	421.
Within Groups	17-1	9518. 652	81. 356		
Total	19-1	333. 9812	-		

Table value (Q) at a degree of freedom (2, 117) and a level of significance (0.05) = (3. 08) approx.

It is noted in Table No. (8) that the value of (F) extracted was (1. 805), which is smaller than the tabular value (F) of (3. 08) at a degree of freedom (2, 117) and a level of significance (0.05), and this means that there are no statistically significant differences from the perspective of the sample members about the role of institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the variable of the educational qualification.

Identify the nature of the differences in the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society from the perspective of their employees, according to the variable of the job grade.

To find out the significance of the difference between the arithmetic means of the responses of the sample of workers on the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society, according to the job grade variable, the analysis of unilateral variance (ANOVA) was used and Table No. (9) shows this.

Table No (9): (ANOVA) to find out the differences in the role of institutions from the perspective of employees according to the job grade

Test	Degree of freedom	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F value	Significance level
Between Groups	3	3414. 836	1138. 279	20. 639*	.001
Within Groups	116	6397. 497	55. 151		
Total	119	333. 9812	-		

Table value (Q) at a degree of freedom (3, 116) and a level of significance (0. 05) = (2. Almost 50?

*** A function at a significance level (0. 05)**

It is noted in Table No. (9) that the value of (F) extracted was (20. 639), which is greater than the tabular value (q) of (2. 50) degrees, at a degree of freedom (3, 116) and a level of significance (0. 05), and this means that there are statistically significant differences from the perspective of the sample members, about the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the job grade variable. To find out who these differences were, the post-test (LSD) was used, and Table No. (10) shows this.

Table No (10): Differences in the post-test on the role of institutions from the perspective of workers according to the job

Variable (A)	Variable (B)	c = sum (a) and (b)	Significance level
Head of Department	Employee	11111.11	014.0
Department Manager	Employee	52137.21	001.0
	Head of Department	41026.10	002.0
General Manager	Employee	73016.16	003.0

It is noted in Table No. (10) that the differences were in favor of the holders of the job grades (head of the department), (director of the department), and (director general), and at the job grades (employee), as well as there were differences in favor of the holders of the job grade (director of the department), and at the holders of the job grade (head of the department), meaning that in general, the holders of the job grade (employee) are the least who believe that the role of official institutions in providing care for persons with physical disabilities and integrating them into Yemeni society is appropriate and large and that the most who believe that their role was large are (directors of departments) more than others and then general managers.

Identify the nature of the differences in the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society from the perspective of their employees according to the variable duration of service.

To find out the significance of the difference between the arithmetic averages of the responses of the sample of workers on the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of the disabled in Yemeni society, according to the variable of the period of service (less than 5 years, 5-10 years, 11-15 years, more than 15 years), a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used, and Table No. (11) shows this.

Table No (11): (ANOVA) to find out the differences in the role of institutions from the perspective of employees, Depending on the length of service

Test	Degree of freedom	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F value	Significance level
Between Groups	3	521. 319	173. 773	2. 169*	379
Within Groups	116	9291.015	80. 095		
Total	119	333. 9812	-		

Table value (Q) at a degree of freedom (3, 116) and a level of significance (0. 05) = (2. Almost 50?

It is noted in Table No. (11) that the value of (F) extracted was (2. 169), which is smaller than the tabular value (F) of (2. 50) at a degree of freedom (3, 116) and a level of significance (0.05), and this means that there are no statistically significant differences from the perspective of the sample of workers in official institutions about the role of institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the variable of the period of service.

CONCLUSION

- The role of Yemeni official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in society, from the perspective of their employees in all the axes covered by the research (health, educational, functional, and political integration) came with an average estimate, in terms of the arithmetic average of (3.02), a standard deviation of (1.14), and a percentage of (60.4%).
- It was found that there were no statistically significant differences from the perspective of the sample of employees of Yemeni official institutions, about the role of institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the gender variable, and according to the educational qualification variable, the governorate variable, the academic qualification, and the duration of service.
- It became clear that there are statistically significant differences from the perspective of the sample of employees in Yemeni official institutions, about the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society according to the job grade variable, in favor of the job grade holders (department manager), and on the job grade holders (head of department), that is, in general, the job grade holders (employee), are the least who believe that the role of official institutions in achieving the social integration of persons with physical disabilities in Yemeni society is medium and large, and that the most who believe that their role was large are department managers more than others and then general managers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Urging the promotion of the participation of persons with disabilities in the activities of society on several bases, the most important of which are: the principle of achieving social justice, equality for all, and equal opportunities, then achieving independence and decent living, including the provision of integrated health services, education from the basic stage to vocational and technical education and higher education.

- Preparing an integrated database on the relevant organizations of the international community in the field of disability at the local, regional, and international levels, to obtain the required funding for some projects and programs in whole or in partnership with other parties or to benefit from the expertise available to them.
- The need to provide job opportunities for the employment of physical-impaired individuals by supporting the contributions made by government institutions and organizations of the international community in capital and granting loans, to facilitate the establishment of production projects for disabled individuals, promote and develop creativity, protect disabled persons from unemployment, and provide them with protection from occupational hazards.
- Developing mechanisms for the implementation of laws on the rehabilitation and employment of persons with disabilities to include the provision of employment opportunities in the private sector, international cooperation, and the mixed sector, by adhering to the prescribed percentage for the employment of persons with disabilities, and encouraging businessmen to provide appropriate employment opportunities for persons with physical disabilities, by facilitating the procedures for their implementation.
- Activating the role of all media to raise the awareness of society of the need to accept this category as an important and effective segment in the development of the renaissance of the nation, in how to deal and cooperate with it, and provide special awareness to the families of these disabled persons and how to deal with their disabled children.
- Demanding the need to issue special legislation for the disabled by the state related to the need for the disabled to obtain a quota of seats in local, parliamentary, and presidential councils that ensures their real participation in political life, ensures their influence on the national arena, and ensures that their rights are not violated in all fields.

SUGGESTIONS

- Preparing educational, health, and vocational rehabilitation programs for the physically disabled, scientifically and deliberately based on the reality of the disabled in our country and their personal, social, and physical abilities, which already ensures the benefit of these programs.
- Conducting a comprehensive survey (statistics) of persons with disabilities in Yemen at the governorate level, then the directorates, isolation, and villages, through which (governorate, directorate, isolation, gender, age, type of disability, degree of disability, cause of disability, needs, problems) are determined.
- Coordinating efforts between various universities, scientific disciplines, research centers, and studies to study disability in its various aspects and to identify needs and search for solutions to alleviate the problems suffered by persons with disabilities by communicating them to decision-makers in government institutions and international community organizations.

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